

The FAIR Principles

Findable – What?

- F1: (Meta) data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers
- F2: data are described with rich metadata
- F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe
- F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

Findable – How?

Data can be Findable by:

- Adding a persistent identifier -PID (e.g. DOI) that is global and unique
- Adding rich metadata, which are relevant for both humans and machines to access, understand, and process data
- Differentiating between metadata and dataset itself
- Uploading data into a data repository

Accessible – What?

- A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
- A1.1The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
- A1.2The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
- A2. Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

Accessible – How?

Data can be Accessible by:

- Retrieving data by ‘clicking on a link’, without specialized tools or communication methods (http, ftp): Anyone with a computer and an internet connection can access at least the metadata.
- If you can't publish data openly, you should provide access to the metadata
- FAIR data ≠ Open data : Even if the data itself cannot be shared openly, you should create and publish a description of your data so that researchers with a relevant purpose can request permission to access

Interoperable – What?

- I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
- I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

Interoperable – How?

Data can be Interoperable by:

- Having a standard way to describe itself to whoever (machine or human) tries to access it without a need for a translator or mappings (common Format: JSON, RDF...)
- Using vocabularies and ontologies (each metadata field has its definition, and a meaningful relation among them and their constraints)
- Using a well-defined framework to describe and structure (meta)data→to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources

Reusable – What?

- R1. (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
- R1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
- R1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
- R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

Reusable – How?

Data can be Reusable by:

- Adding documentation that helps others understand the data
- Adding an appropriate data license that determines how data can be reused
- Adding rich metadata that describes the context under which the data was generated (Provenance means to describe the origin of data -Who? What? When? How?)
- Considering which usage rights you want to attach to your data -to what extent is the data useful for others?